

ISic0424

Funerary inscription of Burnia Primula

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 240

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [D(is)] M(anibus) s(acrum)
2. Burniae · L(uci) · f(iliae)
3. Primulae
4. [E]paphroditu[s]
5. Augustoru[m]
6. [li]b(ertus) v(ixit) a(nnos) []

Apparatus

Text from CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491652

EDCS 21900486

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7144 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0424. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335618>